

The General Theory of Relativity, a New Iteration

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Abstract

A general theory of relativity is formulated without Einstein's equation. Einstein's tensor ties the space metric to the stress-energy tensor of a gravitational field. A homogeneous isotropic field metric is under consideration. In particular, the metric for a homogeneous isotropic universe possesses the anticipated density of our own universe. The speed of time progression at a distance from the observer slows according to an acceleration law asymptotically equal to Hubble's Law. A continuous field is homogeneous within the limits of small domains. This makes it possible to write a metric for a general continuous field and the single parameter given by the wave equation. The Schwarzschild problem has a continuous solution for $r > 0$. This solution approaches the Schwarzschild solution beyond the Schwarzschild radius and a second solution is obtained from the Schwarzschild problem - a stationary, expulsive, self-consistent field.

Keywords: General Relativity Theory, Gravity field equation, exact solution, Stress-energy solution, Homogeneous universe, Dark energy.

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1. Introduction

The general theory of relativity is a groundbreaking creation. We refuse to believe that it has flaws, although they are widely known. It is the singularity of the solution and the absence of a local conservation law.

If we consider the matter of the general theory of relativity, it has two key components.

Equation of motion: This describes the motion of a test body in curvilinear coordinates, whether that motion be along a curved line in ordinary space or the body's accelerated fall in Riemannian space. The equation of motion does not include the test body's mass, which is understandable, as it has been common knowledge since Galileo's time that free fall acceleration is independent of mass. We call this the equivalence principle of gravitational and inertial mass. The equation of motion does include the components of the metric tensor of spacetime.

The gravitational field equation is needed to find the spacetime metric, distorted by the masses present. In some of the simplest cases, the metric can be found using basic principles but generally requires the gravitational field equation.

This equation is now commonly known as Einstein's equation [1]. The left-hand side depends on the components of the space metric and their derivatives. It is known as Einstein's tensor and possesses an important property—its covariant derivative equals zero. On the other hand, this zero covariant derivative for the stress-energy tensor fulfills the laws of conservation of a physical system as described by the stress-energy tensor and makes the following equation possible

$$\text{Einstein's tensor} = k \times \text{stress-energy tensor},$$

where $k = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}$ is the coefficient and G is the gravitational constant.

A considerable challenge arises here. The law of energy conservation demands that the stress-energy tensor include both the energy of matter and the energy of the gravitational field [2]. Strictly speaking, solving this equation is the only method of calculating the energy of the gravitational field. Over

the course of approximately two years, Einstein attempted to solve this problem but found no solution for it in its original form. Finally, he discovered an easy solution—he simply removed the gravitational field energy from the right-hand side. Guides about the theory of general relativity very rarely note this circumstance. Only in L. D. Landau and E. M. Lifshitz's [1] course can one find evidence of it. **In § 95. Einstein's Equations**, "Gravitational interaction plays a role only for bodies with a sufficiently large mass (because of the smallness of the gravitational constant), and therefore, in studying the gravitational field, we usually have to deal with macroscopic bodies." Thus, Einstein's equation proved to be incomplete:

$$\text{Einstein's tensor} = k \times \text{stress-energy tensor} \\ \text{without the gravitational field energy}$$

Nonetheless, Einstein's equation has been extremely useful and works wonderfully. It is my opinion, however, that the reason behind the theory's shortcomings lies in this equation and the chances of "correcting" this equation are extremely low, as Einstein spent at least two years, and quite possibly the rest of his life, on this.

At this point, it is appropriate to cite the opinion of the theory's creator, as expressed in final published work [3]. Einstein cautions against the unjustifiably increasing the dimension of space, introducing fields of a different sort in addition to the tensor field, and imposing higher-order field equations. Einstein speaks further on the need to rid the theory of singularities.

"Field theory is not yet fully defined by a system of field equations. Is it necessary to recognize the existence of singularities? Should boundary conditions be postulated? As for the first question, **my view is that singularities should be excluded. It does not seem reasonable to me to introduce into the continuum theory points (or lines, etc.) for which the field equations are not satisfied.** In addition, introducing singularities is equivalent to postulating boundary conditions (arbitrary in terms of

field equations) on the ‘surfaces’ surrounding these singularities. Without such an assumption, the theory would be too vague. The answer to the second question, in my opinion, is that postulating boundary conditions is mandatory.”

We will try to follow the theory’s basic principles.

- ❖ First, this is the **principle of relativity**. It essentially amounts to the independence of the local speed of light from the reference system.
- ❖ The **equivalence principle** ties the gravitational field to the inertia field via a shared acceleration field.
- ❖ **The conformity principle** links various theories, such as Newton’s theory of gravitation and the general relativity theory.
- ❖ **Conservation laws** are essential for any complete physical theory.
- ❖ Finally, the key principle... **Energy is the source of the gravitational field, including the energy of the field itself**. The gravitational field energy tensor is the source of the gravitational field. On this matter, Einstein said, “this is an obviously necessary requirement, as the gravitational influence of the system cannot depend on the physical nature of the energy that serves as the source of the field.”

2. Methods

2.1 Energy of a Gravitational Field

The covariant divergence of **Einstein’s tensor** $G_{ik} = R_{ik} - \frac{1}{2}g_{ik}R$ equals zero. In other words, Einstein’s tensor possesses properties of the stress–energy–momentum tensor. The coefficient linking the stress–energy tensor and Einstein’s tensor is known. Systematic application of general relativity principles leads us to conclude that a stress–energy tensor of the gravitational field must exist and is expressed through Einstein’s tensor

$$\mathfrak{T}_{ik} = \frac{c^4}{8\pi G} G_{ik}.$$

For instance, the stress–energy tensor of a field in the absence of matter (in empty space)

$$t_{ik} = \frac{c^4}{8\pi G} G_{ik}. \quad (1)$$

However, this is incompatible with Einstein’s equation for empty space

$$G_{ik} = 0. \quad (2)$$

Therefore, we are forced to reject Einstein’s equation...

Let’s see how the theory looks without Einstein’s equation, but with the complete set of principles for the general relativity theory.

Figure 1. An attempt to depict the change in spacetime scales along a geodesic homogeneous field. [4-6]

2.2 Homogeneous Field

An example of a problem for which the gravitational field equation is not needed is the determination of the metric for a homogeneous field.

Einstein [7] considered the homogeneous gravitational field in 1907. However, he found only the exact relationship between the time of the inertial system and proper time. Einstein achieved this using

only the constancy of the speed of light. In contemporary designations, the result is:

$$ds^2 = e^{\frac{2gx}{c^2}} c^2 dt^2 \dots$$

Harry Lass described a homogeneous acceleration field, which was also derived from the constancy of the speed of light

$$ds^2 = e^{\frac{2gx}{c^2}} (c^2 dt^2 - dx^2) - dy^2 - dz^2. \quad (3)$$

Lass examined a one-dimensional problem. The choice for the two “extra” measurements is somewhat arbitrary. Lass chose anisotropic 3D space and his metric satisfies Einstein’s equation (2).

Lass’s metric has spatial anisotropy of the speed of light. However, we have no reason to reject the isotropy of space. The homogeneous isotropic space metric defines a space in which the speed of light is constant and independent of direction

$$ds^2 = e^{\frac{2gx}{c^2}} (c^2 dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2). \quad (4)$$

Unlike metric (3), this metric has a non-zero Einstein tensor, meaning we can pair it with the stress-energy tensor (1).

It is easy to imagine what the homogeneous isotropic field metric will look like overall

$$ds^2 = \exp \frac{2g_i x_i}{c^2} [(dx_0)^2 - (dx_1)^2 - (dx_2)^2 - (dx_3)^2]. \quad (5)$$

where the 4th vector g_i is constant with the acceleration dimension.

Acceleration of a homogeneous field in an isotropic space is calculated using a simple equation [8]:

$$\frac{d^2 x^i}{dt^2} = c^2 \Gamma_{00}^i = \text{const.}$$

As expected, acceleration is constant.

The stress-energy tensor of a homogeneous field with acceleration $(0, g_1, 0, 0)$ likewise does not depend on the coordinates:

$$t_{ik} = \frac{c^4}{8\pi G} G_{ik} = \frac{g_1^2}{8\pi G} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \text{const.}$$

The energy density of the homogeneous field $t_{00} = -\frac{g_1^2}{8\pi G}$ for metric (4) coincides with the energy density of a gravitational field in the Newtonian method [1].

One can imagine how the Cartesian space tangents of a homogeneous isotropic field might appear geometrically similar to one another (Fig. 1).

2.3 Special Case: The Metric of a Homogeneous Universe

If $g_0 \neq 0$ and $g_1 = g_2 = g_3 = 0$, the metric of a homogeneous isotropic field is

$$ds^2 = \exp(2g_0 t) [c^2 (dx_0)^2 - (dx_1)^2 - (dx_2)^2 - (dx_3)^2].$$

This metric has a unique non-zero parameter, the dimension of which is equal to that of the Hubble constant. A natural candidate for the role of the constant $2g_0$ is the Hubble constant H_0

$$ds^2 = \exp(H_0 t) [c^2 (dx_0)^2 - (dx_1)^2 - (dx_2)^2 - (dx_3)^2]. \quad (6)$$

Let’s imagine a universe described by this metric. Clocks in such a space slow in proportion to their distance from the observation point. This metric describes a space with a rapidly growing red shift asymptotically (within the limit of small t) equal to Hubble’s law.

$$z = \exp(H_0 t) - 1 \approx H_0 t,$$

where t is the time of light propagation.

Einstein’s tensor lets us calculate the stress-energy tensor containing the energy density of that space and the negative pressure

$$t_{ik} = \frac{c^4}{8\pi G} \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

It follows that the density of a homogeneous space coincides with the expected sum of dark matter and dark energy densities (the Friedmann–Lemaître–Robertson–Walker metric):

$$t_{00} = \rho = \frac{3H_0^2}{8\pi G}$$

This energy density is what they call dark matter.

Dark energy is, by its nature, homogeneous. Like all energy, dark energy possesses gravitational properties and is likely attracted to large accumulations of matter (Fig. 2). These concentrations are associated with observable dark matter.

Figure 2. NCC 4414 Galaxy. Galaxies as the centers of attraction for dark matter. We register accumulations of dark energy as dark matter. Image: The Hubble Heritage Team (AURA/STScI/NASA) NASA Headquarters - Greatest Images of NASA (NASA-HQ-GRIN). [9]

The presented image conforms poorly with the present-day system of cosmological hypotheses. Regardless, such a metric exists. It is homogeneous and gives the correct correlation between Hubble's constant and the universe's density. In addition, we see a deviation from Hubble's law, which corresponds to observations.

2.4 Continuous Field Metric

We discovered that, in special cases, it is possible to find the metric for the gravitational field without the gravitational field equation. However, it is clear that this equation is necessary.

The homogeneity of the field strength vector \mathbf{g} in a sufficiently small volume is a trivial fact that results

from the field's continuity. We can conclude from this that the metric of a continuous field in this limit must be a metric of a homogeneous field.

In fact, we will select an area of the gravitational field $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{r})$ radius ε , including the point \mathbf{r}_0 . Any continuous field within the limit $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ is homogeneous, i.e. the field strength is constant in sufficiently small spaces. This follows direction from the definition of the continuity of a function. Indeed, for any $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $\delta > 0$, such that for any \mathbf{r}

$$|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0| < \delta \Rightarrow |\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{r}) - \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{r}_0)| < \varepsilon.$$

Note that the gravitational field is continuous, even at the medium-vacuum boundary. Consequently, the gravitational field metric at this point is asymptotically equal to the metric of a homogeneous field (5).

This satisfies the requirement for local homogeneity in an isotropic space by using the metrics in the form of

$$ds^2 = f^2 (c^2 dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2), \quad (7)$$

where $f = \exp \frac{h}{c^2}$, with h being the continuous coordinate function in the metric's domain. The local speed of light at this point does not depend on the selection of this point, which is a key point in the relativity principle. However, the speed of light may depend on the gravitational potential from the point of view of a remote observer.

It is easy to see that the multitude of possible metrics for a gravitational field form a multiplicative group with the parameter $f > 0$, $f \in R$. In fact, if the product of the two parameters $f_1 f_2$ is in the form of metric (7), then the metric

$$(f_1 f_2)^2 (c^2 dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2)$$

represent the metric (7) form.

It is also important to us that the parameter $h \in R$ forms an additive group.

2.5 Gravitational Field Equation

The scalar parametric equation, which forms the additive group, should be linear and the simplest

generally covariant linear equation is the wave equation.

In arbitrary coordinates, the target metric (7) is written as:

$$ds^2 = \exp \frac{2h}{c^2} \eta_{ik} dx_i dx_k. \quad (8)$$

with η_{ik} being the linear element of a plane space. In that case, the simplest generally covariant equation for scalar h is

$$\square h = -4\pi GT. \quad (9)$$

The simplest, nontrivial solution to this equation is the linear coordinate function $h = g_i x^i$, i.e. the metric tensor of a homogeneous field (5), including the homogeneous universe metric (6). In the non-relativistic limit, the equation (9) turns into Poisson's equation, while metric (8) becomes the Minkowski metric. In this manner, these equations and metrics satisfy the conformity principle.

2.6 Gravitational Field Metric of a Point Mass

We will examine the Schwarzschild problem of locating a stationary field of a point mass. Schwarzschild's solution [1] utilizes the symmetry of the problem and Einstein's vacuum equation for this purpose. We are using the equation for the field metric parameter (9) to solve this problem.

The metric in spherical coordinates

$$ds^2 = \exp \left[\frac{2h(r)}{c^2} \right] (c^2 dt^2 - dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2).$$

Equation (9) in a stationary instance becomes Poisson's equation

$$\Delta h = 0,$$

which has a known solution in spherical coordinates

$$h = \frac{C_1}{r} + C_2.$$

As a rule, we assume that the field, at infinity, approaches the Newtonian field. Take $C_2 = 0$ and $C_1 = \pm r_g$. Here $r_g = \frac{2GM}{c^2}$, while M is the total mass

and is one of the solutions to the Schwarzschild problem.

$$ds^2 = e^{-\frac{r_g}{r}} (c^2 dt^2 - dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2). \quad (10)$$

One might expect this metric to be asymptotically equal to the Schwarzschild metric, but this is not the case.

Figure 3. The relationship between gravity and the distance to a point mass. Newton's law is the dashed line, Schwarzschild's solution is the dot-and-dash line, and the exact solution is the solid line. The image in the rectangle is stretched to fifty times the size of the graph plot. [4]

Effects observed in moderate fields for solution (10) and the Schwarzschild solution are practically the identical, since the Christoffel symbols $\Gamma_{i,kl}$ included in the geodesic equation are asymptotically equal (see the Table) for both equations, with the single exception being Γ_{111} , which is significant only for notable radial velocities. This fact lets us compare solution (10) to the Schwarzschild solution for eccentric orbits of cosmic bodies, as an example.

If the absolute value of free fall acceleration (field strength) is g_1 in the direction x^1 , and F^1 and F_1 are contra- and covariant vectors of this acceleration, then we find from the equation of motion in curvilinear coordinates [10, 11] that acceleration is relative to the initial reference system

$$g_1 = c^2 \sqrt{F^1 F_1} = c^2 \sqrt{\frac{\Gamma_{100}}{g_{00} g_{11}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma_{100}}{g_{00}}} c^2 \frac{\Gamma_{100}}{g_{00} \sqrt{g_{11}}}.$$

Gravity acceleration obtained from metric (10) is asymptotically equal to that obtained from the Schwarzschild metric. In fact, we may compare the pull of gravity found from metric (10)

$$g_r = -\frac{GM}{r^2} e^{\frac{GM}{c^2 r}} \quad (11)$$

with the familiar Schwarzschild result

$$g_s = -\frac{GM}{r^2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}}.$$

Therefore, despite the external dissimilarity, metric (10) describes the observed effects in moderate fields precisely in the same manner as the Schwarzschild metric. We can see in Figure 3 that these field strengths differ considerably only near the Schwarzschild radius, for example, on the surface of neutron stars. Here, the new solution appears innocuous, when, in fact, field strength grows extremely quickly in areas of strong fields—more quickly than any exponential function.

2.7 Solution Superposition

Parameter h is the solution to the linear equation, to which the superposition principle applies.

Massive objects in the universe are not located in empty space, but rather against a dark energy background. In this case, superposition of solutions (6) and (10) describes a field in proximity to massive objects:

$$ds^2 = \exp\left(H_0 t - \frac{r_g}{r}\right) [c^2(dx_0)^2 - (dx_1)^2 - (dx_2)^2 - (dx_3)^2].$$

Figure 5. Fermi Bubbles. It is quite likely that a expulsive gravitational field is speeding up the penetrating radiation of these bubbles. The most penetrating forms of radiation (marked in light blue) are observed from the center of the bubbles from Earth. (Image: NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center). [4, 12]

Figure 6. Fermi Bubbles². (Image: NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center). [13]

² In 2010, gamma-ray observations by Fermi revealed previously unknown features in our galaxy that stretch halfway across the sky. Now called the Fermi Bubbles, these mysterious structures (magenta in the image above) emerge above and below the center of our galaxy, spanning a total length of about 50,000 light-years. [13]

Figure 4. Vacuum solutions (12) for an expulsive field α with the varying “masses” μ of a gravitational field.

2.8 Expulsive Fields

We have no reason to reject the second solution to Schwarzschild’s problem, which is opposite in sign to the scalar parameter

The plane of our galaxy (shown in blue above) glows brightly in gamma rays, which result when high-energy particles called cosmic rays interact with gas and dust. The Fermi Bubbles emit higher-energy gamma rays than the rest of the galaxy’s disk. (In the interactive, clicking on the Gamma-ray Catalog button changes the background to an all-sky view of this so-called diffuse emission). [13]

The bubbles may be related to the release of vast amounts of energy emitted from the supermassive black hole at the center of our Milky Way galaxy. We know that in other galaxies, supermassive black holes that ingest large amounts of matter can power high-energy jets. It’s possible the Milky Way’s central black hole went through such a phase in the past, producing jets responsible for the Fermi Bubbles we see today. [13]

A completely unexpected discovery like the Fermi Bubbles is a special treat. However, scientists know that there are many more surprises waiting to be uncovered by Fermi. In the most recent catalog of sources from Fermi’s Large Area Telescope, fully a third of detected source positions are not known to have a gamma-ray emitting object at that location. What could be producing these gamma rays? [13]

That’s the question many scientists are hoping to answer as Fermi continues its mission. [13]

$$h = \frac{1}{r} \frac{2G\mu}{c^2}.$$

with this metric

$$ds^2 = e^{\frac{r_g}{r}} (c^2 dt^2 - dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2).$$

In this case, the force of “gravity” is directed outwards:

$$g_r = \frac{G\mu}{r^2} e^{-\frac{G\mu}{c^2 r}}. \quad (12)$$

This kind of stationary field has no features, including at its origin. Moreover, within the limit $r \rightarrow 0$, the field disappears (Fig. 4). There is no need to postulate the presence of negative mass, which would be undesirable—the field’s intrinsic negative energy is its source. The scalar curvature of metric (12) equals zero at its origin, since there is no mass at the center of this formation and the dimensional parameter of mass μ can take any positive value (Fig. 4). In a distant zone, the strength approaches Newton’s law, with the only difference being that this gravitational bubble field has an opposing direction.

This solution describes an expulsive gravitational field without a principal source. Its source is the field itself. Parameter μ has a mass dimension.

Fermi Bubbles serve as an example of objects with expulsive potential and have been observed near our galaxy (see Figures (5) and (6)). The central areas of these bubbles emit stronger penetrating radiation. This confirms that the inferred structure of these bubbles is an expulsive field.

2.9 Anisotropic Fields

The equation for isotropic space does not describe all fields, as in the example of gravitational waves. The scalar parametric equation, in this case, substitutes the equation for the h_i^k tensor. Now the vacuum equation coincides with the weak gravitational wave equation.

$$\square h_{ik} = 0. \quad (13)$$

The solution to this equation is known [1]. However, a solution substitution (13) for the metric

$$ds^2 = \exp \frac{2h_{ik}}{c^2} \eta_{ik} dx_i dx_k$$

should give an accurate description of the gravitational waves in empty space.

10. Conclusions

The concept of a uniform field led us to a new view of our Universe as a stationary object. In this

surprising way was found an explanation of the accelerated Hubble law, dark energy and dark matter.

The gravitational field equation, alternative to the Einstein equation, is constructed. The solutions of the equation correspond to empirical data, but do not contain singularities. In addition, solutions lead to a local law of conservation of energy and momentum.

We hope that in the near future the theory will be further developed.

Table 1. Comparison between results from Schwarzschild Metric and New Solution.

Schwarzschild Metric	New Solution
$\Gamma_{100} = -\Gamma_{001} = -\Gamma_{010} = -\frac{r_g c^2}{2r^2}$	$\Gamma_{100} = -\Gamma_{001} = -\Gamma_{010} = -\frac{r_g c^2}{2r^2} e^{-\frac{r_g}{r}}$
$\Gamma_{111} = \frac{r_g}{2(r - r_g)^2}$	$\Gamma_{111} = -\frac{r_g}{2r^2} e^{-\frac{r_g}{r}}$
$\Gamma_{122} = -\Gamma_{212} = -\Gamma_{221} = r$	$\Gamma_{122} = -\Gamma_{212} = -\Gamma_{221} = \left(r + \frac{1}{2}r_g\right) e^{-\frac{r_g}{r}}$
$\Gamma_{133} = -\Gamma_{313} = -\Gamma_{331} = r \sin^2 \theta$	$\Gamma_{133} = -\Gamma_{313} = -\Gamma_{331} = \left(r + \frac{1}{2}r_g\right) \sin^2 \theta e^{-\frac{r_g}{r}}$
$\Gamma_{233} = -\Gamma_{313} = -\Gamma_{331} = r^2 \sin \theta \cos \theta$	$\Gamma_{233} = -\Gamma_{313} = -\Gamma_{331} = r^2 \sin \theta \cos \theta e^{-\frac{r_g}{r}}$

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